

LLM Self-Explanations as Design Material: Toward a Taxonomy

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Abstract

Researchers and practitioners routinely manipulate properties of LLM self-explanations (their length, tone, confidence, structure) yet these design choices remain implicit and inconsistently named across studies. Without shared vocabulary, we cannot systematically compare findings, replicate studies, or accumulate knowledge about which explanation properties affect user outcomes. We present a preliminary taxonomy of six categories of self-explanation properties drawn from the XAI and HCI literature: surface, relational, structural, delivery, source, and semantic properties. For each category, we identify key properties with empirical grounding from studies that explicitly manipulated these properties. We offer this taxonomy as a starting point for more rigorous research on LLM self-explanation design and invite community feedback to refine it.

CCS Concepts

• **Human-centered computing** → **Empirical studies in HCI**; • **Computing methodologies** → *Natural language generation*.

Keywords

explainable AI, large language models, chain-of-thought, taxonomy, explanation design

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1 Introduction

Large language models (LLMs) increasingly produce self-explanations alongside their outputs: chain-of-thought traces, justifications for decisions, or accounts of why a particular answer was given. By self-explanation we mean any language-based communication from the model to the user that intends to make its reasoning or behavior more transparent [12]. For the vast number of end users of LLM products, these self-explanations have become the primary way they encounter some insights of the LLM's output and potentially

calibrate their level of trust. LLM self-explanation is a fast-growing research area, as traditional XAI approaches become less viable at the scale of LLMs [1, 10, 25].

We argue that, like any form of AI explanations, LLM self-explanations are designed artifacts. Researchers and practitioners need to decide, for example, how long generated explanations should be, how confident they should sound, whether to present reasoning as linear steps or branching alternatives, and when to reveal information progressively versus all at once. Crucially, LLM self-explanations do not necessarily reflect the model's reasoning faithfully [15, 27]. As a result, self-explanations need to be carefully designed in order to provide value to end users.

While much existing research on self-explanations is technical in nature [1, 12], all self-explanations require decisions on what forms they take, whether these decisions are taken deliberately or otherwise. Yet very often these design choices remain largely implicit. Furthermore, the research community currently lacks consistent terminologies to describe various properties of self-explanations. For example, one study might report that they vary "verbosity" of explanations, while another calls similar constructs "elaboration" or "detail level." A lack of taxonomy of self-explanations also makes it difficult for researchers to isolate variables in controlled user studies.

In this paper, we propose a preliminary taxonomy of LLM self-explanation properties towards a unified vocabulary for this design space. Drawing on XAI, HCI, and related fields, we identify six categories of self-explanation properties that researchers have manipulated in empirical studies. For each category, we highlight key properties and illustrate them with empirical studies that manipulated those properties and measured user outcomes. In doing so, the taxonomy can also serve as a structured lens for surveying this rapidly evolving field, helping to identify where empirical evidence exists and where it remains sparse.

2 Background and Approach

Recent surveys on LLM explainability focus primarily on technical methods for generating explanations [3, 22, 30], with Cambria et al. [3] noting explicitly that current explanations are "often too complex for non-technical stakeholders" and calling for work on the "presentation layer." Schneider [25] takes a broader view, proposing dimensions like interaction scope and personalization, though acknowledging limited coverage of how humans respond to different

explanation designs. Meyer and Zhu [20] analyzed the interface design of existing XAI systems. In parallel, empirical HCI studies have documented that explanation properties affect user outcomes [6, 13], yet use inconsistent terminology that makes cross-study comparison difficult. Our work builds directly on these surveys and synthesizes various human-facing properties of self-explanations into a consistent taxonomy.

Our preliminary taxonomy emerged iteratively, moving between bottom-up engagement with empirical studies and top-down theoretical reasoning about meaningful categories. We collected studies from XAI, HCI, and related fields that explicitly manipulated explanation properties, then organized related properties into categories through affinity diagramming as well refining category boundaries through ongoing group discussions.

Because LLM self-explanations are recent, many studies we draw on predate LLMs or address traditional XAI methods. However, the properties they manipulate (e.g., explanation length or expressed confidence) concern the human-facing explanation, not the generation method, and we note where transferability may be limited. We do not claim the resulting categories are orthogonal or exhaustive.

3 A Preliminary Taxonomy of LLM Self-Explanations

We organize LLM self-explanation properties into six categories, see Table 1. For each, we describe what the category captures and illustrate it with properties where researchers have explicitly manipulated that property and measured user outcomes.

3.1 Surface Properties

We define surface properties as those **most immediate linguistic features** of self-explanations, such as length, level of detail, and stylistic register. Users often treat these as heuristics for quality, making them consequential for trust even when they carry no information about accuracy. Steyvers et al. [26] varied explanation length while holding content constant and found that longer explanations increased user confidence without adding useful information. Linder et al. [18] varied the amount of supplemental explanation in a fact-checking system—from no additional detail, to feature-importance indicators, to feature-importance plus supporting examples—and found that more detail improved users’ understanding of the model but at the cost of additional processing time. A third property is stylistic register (e.g., formal versus conversational), which concerns lexical and syntactic choices independent of an explanation’s propositional content.

3.2 Relational Properties

Relational properties concern how **explanations position the LLM relative to the user**: how confident or uncertain the system appears, how warm or clinical its tone, whether it frames itself as authority or collaborator. Where surface-level register concerns how text is written, tone concerns the interpersonal relationship being constructed between system and user. This boundary is not always clean. Okoso et al. [23] varied six explanation styles they collectively call “tone,” but the conditions span both register-level manipulations (formal, simple) and interpersonal ones (humorous, romantic, attractive), illustrating the distinction this taxonomy aims

to make explicit. Kim et al. [13] compared first-person hedging (“I’m not sure, but...”) against impersonal framing (“It’s not clear, but...”) in LLM-generated explanations and found that first-person hedging decreased user confidence and reduced overreliance on wrong answers—an effect moderated by uncertainty level [28] and confidence calibration [17]. Li et al. [16] found that user confidence aligned with AI-expressed confidence regardless of actual correctness, with Okoso et al. [24] further showing that explanation tone (e.g., authoritative versus humorous) influenced actual decisions, not just perceptions, depending on the AI’s role and user attributes.

3.3 Structural Properties

Structural properties concern the **logical organization** of an explanation: what information is included, in what order, and how the parts relate to each other. Structure has played a central role in traditional XAI, but many of those structural distinctions (e.g., feature importance plots versus example retrieval) do not directly apply to LLM self-explanations, leaving this category empirically less explored. One exception is Malaviya et al. [19], who compared different LLM-generated rationale formats and found that format affected both user feedback quality and perceived trustworthiness, offering early evidence that structural choices shape user outcomes. Related but distinct, Yao et al. [29] demonstrated that branching reasoning paths improve LLM problem-solving over linear chains of thought, but whether exposing users to such structures affects comprehension or trust remains untested—as do other structural choices such as reasoning order and whether rejected alternatives are surfaced.

3.4 Delivery Properties

Delivery properties govern the **mechanics of how explanations reach users**: timing, modality, and interactivity. Unlike structural properties (what and how much to include), delivery concerns when and how content is revealed. For instance, He et al. [11] compared two delivery modalities for the same underlying explanations: a static dashboard versus a conversational interface. The conversational format increased both perceived understanding and overreliance, with LLM-powered agents amplifying this effect, illustrating that how an explanation is delivered can shape user behavior independently of its content. Progressive disclosure is another delivery property. Muralidhar et al. [21] found that presenting an initial explanation snippet with the option to request further detail on demand improved users’ ability to follow AI reasoning compared to presenting all information at once. Similarly, explanation timing shapes trust: Chen et al. [5] showed that whether explanations appear before, after, or alongside a recommendation produces different trust outcomes.

3.5 Source Properties

Source properties concern **provenance**: what generated the explanation and whether it includes verifiable references. Chain-of-thought explanations can systematically misrepresent what actually influenced outputs: for instance, when biasing features such as answer ordering are introduced into prompts, models generate plausible reasoning that supports the biased answer without mentioning the bias [27]. Larger models produce less faithful traces [15], and

Category	What it captures	Example properties
Surface	Linguistic features noticed before processing meaning	Length [26], detail [18], register [23]
Relational	How the explanation positions the LLM relative to the user	Uncertainty [13], confidence [16], tone [24]
Structural	Logical organization of the explanation	Rationale format [19], reasoning paths [29]
Delivery	Mechanics of how explanations reach users	Disclosure [21], modality [11], timing [5]
Source	Provenance and faithfulness	CoT faithfulness [27], citations [14]
Semantic	What the explanation is actually about	Coherence [14], completeness [8], scope [4]

Table 1: Overview of the six categories of LLM self-explanation properties.

Figure 1: A map of the six properties on an LLM explanation. The explanation is directly adapted from Claude, but slightly edited for brevity and anonymity.

even models specifically trained with extended chain-of-thought reasoning (such as Claude 3.7 Sonnet and DeepSeek R1) fail to acknowledge biasing influences in their reasoning the majority of the time [7]. Whether explanations include verifiable references also matters: Kim et al. [14] found that clickable sources reduced overreliance on incorrect answers, even though only 26% of participants clicked them, suggesting that the mere presence of citations induces caution. Together, these findings reveal a tension in explanation design: explanations that faithfully report what influenced an output may not yet be technically achievable, while explanations that sound plausible can actively mislead users into overreliance.

3.6 Semantic Properties

Semantic properties concern **what the explanation is actually about**: its scope (local as in instance-specific, versus global as in model- or data-level behavior), completeness, and internal logical coherence. Unlike surface properties (perceived before understanding the explanation) or structural properties (concerning reasoning

organization), semantic properties require users to make sense of the explanation’s meaning. Cau and Spano [4] explicitly varied explanation scope by contrasting local model-centric explanations with global data-centric summaries and hybrid combinations, operationalizing scope as a designable dimension of AI explanations. For coherence, Kim et al. [14] found that logically contradictory LLM-generated explanations reduced overreliance from 83% to 70%, whereas merely incorrect but internally coherent explanations did not. Studies have also manipulated completeness by varying whether explanations are presented in full or only partially [8], or by comparing different explanation strategies against simply displaying the AI’s confidence [2], suggesting that strategic incompleteness can be a deliberate design choice.

Summary of the Taxonomy

Together, these six categories form a design space in which every LLM self-explanation occupies a position along multiple dimensions simultaneously. Figure 1 makes this concrete: a single response to

a scheduling query carries a formal register (surface), high certainty without hedging (relational), reasoning-then-list organization (structural), an expandable thinking block (delivery), a visible chain-of-thought trace (source), and internally coherent references to the user’s context throughout (semantic). The categories are not alternative lenses but concurrent dimensions—any design choice in one interacts with the others, and recognizing this multiplicity is precisely what the taxonomy is intended to support.

4 Discussion

We argue for treating LLM self-explanations as a design material in the interaction design sense [9]: a medium with distinct, manipulable properties whose effects on users can be learned, anticipated, and deliberately shaped. The taxonomy presented here serves as an initial characterization of that material, grounded in empirical findings that already demonstrate how manipulating specific properties influences outcomes like trust and performance. However, the HCI/XAI fields lack a common ground for deliberately designing LLM self-explanations. This preliminary categorization aims to engage HCI/XAI communities in collectively developing this design space.

Our taxonomy is built on existing empirical work, though many examples necessarily draw on pre-LLM AI research. As LLM-specific studies accumulate, we expect both the properties identified here and the categories that organize them to shift — some may merge, others split, and new ones will emerge. The taxonomy maps manipulable properties rather than the user outcomes they produce, though connecting the two is an important next step. We envision a framework responsive to developments in the field.

As the taxonomy subsections illustrate, these categories are not independent; a single design choice often engages multiple categories simultaneously. Therefore, it is not our intention to seek distinct and clearly separated categories, but rather to provide a common vocabulary and a design sensibility, an attentiveness to the fact that explanation properties are choices that require deliberate consideration within a complex and interconnected design space. It is critical for design studies to deliberately vary multiple properties and report design choices transparently so that the research community can gradually build a richer understanding of how these properties function together. This understanding will, in turn, allow both designers and researchers to address user needs in different contexts, sociocultural settings and use cases by designing with a specific sensibility to selected categories towards human-centered LLM self-explanations.

As emphasized throughout this proposal, this is a call for the community to collaborate towards improving this taxonomy. Below, we pose some open questions to guide future discussions.

- The current taxonomy addresses single, static explanations. What happens with agentic systems that must explain trajectories, contingencies, and plans that are genuinely uncertain?
- Historically, explanations are used to improve decision accuracy, and most cited studies measure trust or task performance. Do the same properties matter when the goal of presenting an explanation is reflection, learning, or well-being?

- Are the category names sufficiently distinct to prevent the terminological confusion the taxonomy aims to resolve?
- Properties like register and expressed confidence carry different social meanings across cultural contexts. How should the taxonomy account for culture?

5 Limitations and Future Work

While we present a preliminary taxonomy based on a survey of existing work, we acknowledge future work is needed to validate and extend this work. Building on the discussions in the workshop, we aim to conduct a more extensive systematic literature review of HCI and XAI literature as well as drawing on adjacent fields such as linguistics and communication studies to establish a more robust theoretical foundation for the categorization. Beyond the taxonomy itself, we aim to provide the field with concrete design examples to support application of the taxonomy into future LLM self-explanation design projects.

References

- [1] Chirag Agarwal, Sree Harsha Tanneru, and Himabindu Lakkaraju. 2024. Faithfulness vs. Plausibility: On the (Un)Reliability of Explanations from Large Language Models. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2402.04614* (2024).
- [2] Gagan Bansal, Tongshuang Wu, Joyce Zhou, Raymond Fok, Besmira Nushi, Ece Kamar, Marco Tulio Ribeiro, and Daniel Weld. 2021. Does the Whole Exceed Its Parts? The Effect of AI Explanations on Complementary Team Performance. In *Proceedings of the 2021 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. ACM, 1–16. doi:10.1145/3411764.3445717
- [3] Erik Cambria, Lorenzo Malandri, Fabio Mercorio, Mario Mezzanzanica, and Navid Nobani. 2024. XAI meets LLMs: A Survey of the Relation between Explainable AI and Large Language Models. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2407.15248* (2024).
- [4] Federico Maria Cau and Lucio Davide Spano. 2025. The Influence of Curiosity Traits and On-Demand Explanations in AI-Assisted Decision-Making. In *Proceedings of the 30th International Conference on Intelligent User Interfaces (IUI '25)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 1440–1457. doi:10.1145/3708359.3712165
- [5] Cheng Chen, Mengqi Liao, and S. Shyam Sundar. 2024. When to Explain? Exploring the Effects of Explanation Timing on User Perceptions and Trust in AI Systems. In *Proceedings of the Second International Symposium on Trustworthy Autonomous Systems (TAS '24)*. ACM. doi:10.1145/3686038.3686066
- [6] Valerie Chen, Q. Vera Liao, Jennifer Wortman Vaughan, and Gagan Bansal. 2023. Understanding the Role of Human Intuition on Reliance in Human-AI Decision-Making with Explanations. *Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction* 7, CSCW2, Article 370 (2023). doi:10.1145/3610219
- [7] Yanda Chen, Joe Benton, Ansh Radhakrishnan, Jonathan Uesato, Carson Denison, John Schulman, Arushi Somani, Peter Hase, Misha Wagner, Fabien Roger, Vlad Mikulik, Samuel R. Bowman, Jan Leike, Jared Kaplan, and Ethan Perez. 2025. Reasoning Models Don’t Always Say What They Think. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2505.05410* (2025).
- [8] Sander de Jong, Ville Paananen, Benjamin Tag, and Niels van Berkel. 2025. Cognitive Forcing for Better Decision-Making: Reducing Overreliance on AI Systems Through Partial Explanations. *Proc. ACM Hum.-Comput. Interact.* 9, 2, Article CSCW048 (May 2025), 30 pages. doi:10.1145/3710946
- [9] Graham Dove, Kim Halskov, Jodi Forlizzi, and John Zimmerman. 2017. UX Design Innovation: Challenges for Working with Machine Learning as a Design Material. In *Proceedings of the 2017 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. ACM, 278–288.
- [10] Upol Ehsan, Elizabeth Anne Watkins, Philipp Wintersberger, Carina Manger, Sunnie S. Y. Kim, Niels van Berkel, Andreas Riener, and Mark O. Riedl. 2024. Human-Centered Explainable AI (HCXAI): Reloading Explainability in the Era of Large Language Models (LLMs). In *Extended Abstracts of the CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI EA '24)*. ACM, New York, NY, USA. doi:10.1145/3613905.3636311
- [11] Gaole He, Nilay Aishwarya, and Ujwal Gadiraju. 2025. Is Conversational XAI All You Need? Human-AI Decision Making With a Conversational XAI Assistant. In *Proceedings of the 30th ACM International Conference on Intelligent User Interfaces*. ACM.
- [12] Shiyuan Huang, Siddarth Mamidanna, Shreedhar Jangam, Yilun Zhou, and Leilani H. Gilpin. 2023. Can Large Language Models Explain Themselves? A Study of LLM-Generated Self-Explanations. arXiv:2310.11207 [cs.CL] <https://arxiv.org/abs/2310.11207>

- [13] Sunnie S. Y. Kim, Q. Vera Liao, Mihaela Vorvoreanu, Stephanie Ballard, and Jennifer Wortman Vaughan. 2024. "I'm Not Sure, But...": Examining the Impact of Large Language Models' Uncertainty Expression on User Reliance and Trust. In *Proceedings of the 2024 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency*. ACM, 822–835. doi:10.1145/3630106.3658941
- [14] Sunnie S. Y. Kim, Jennifer Wortman Vaughan, Q. Vera Liao, Tania Lombrozo, and Olga Russakovsky. 2025. Fostering Appropriate Reliance on Large Language Models: The Role of Explanations, Sources, and Inconsistencies. In *Proceedings of the 2025 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. ACM. doi:10.1145/3706598.3714020
- [15] Tamera Lanham, Anna Chen, Ansh Radhakrishnan, Benoit Steiner, Carson Denison, Danny Hernandez, Dustin Li, Esin Durmus, Evan Hubinger, Jackson Kernion, Kamilė Lukosiūtė, Karina Nguyen, Newton Cheng, Nicholas Joseph, Nicholas Schiefer, Oliver Rausch, Robin Larson, Sam McCandlish, Sandipan Kundu, Saurav Kadavath, Shannon Yang, Tom Henighan, Timothy Maxwell, Timothy Telleen-Lawton, Tristan Hume, Zac Hatfield-Dodds, Jared Kaplan, Jan Brauner, Samuel R. Bowman, and Ethan Perez. 2023. Measuring Faithfulness in Chain-of-Thought Reasoning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2307.13702* (2023).
- [16] Jingshu Li, Yitian Yang, Q. Vera Liao, Junti Zhang, and Yi-Chieh Lee. 2025. As Confidence Aligns: Exploring the Effect of AI Confidence on Human Self-confidence in Human-AI Decision Making. In *Proceedings of the 2025 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. ACM. doi:10.1145/3706598.3713336
- [17] Jingshu Li, Yitian Yang, Renwen Zhang, Q. Vera Liao, Tianqi Song, Zhengtao Xu, and Yi-chieh Lee. 2024. Understanding the Effects of Miscalibrated AI Confidence on User Trust, Reliance, and Decision Efficacy. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2402.07632* (2024).
- [18] Rhema Linder, Sina Mohseni, Fan Yang, Shiva K. Pentylala, Eric D. Ragan, and Xia Ben Hu. 2021. How level of explanation detail affects human performance in interpretable intelligent systems: A study on explainable fact checking. *Applied AI Letters* 2, 4 (2021), e49. doi:10.1002/ail.2.49
- [19] Chaitanya Malaviya, Subin Lee, Dan Roth, and Mark Yatskar. 2024. What if you said that differently?: How Explanation Formats Affect Human Feedback Efficacy and User Perception. In *Proceedings of the 2024 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies (Volume 1: Long Papers)*. Association for Computational Linguistics, Mexico City, Mexico, 3046–3065. doi:10.18653/v1/2024.naacl-long.168
- [20] Louie Søs Meyer and Jichen Zhu. 2024. Slide to Explore'What If': An Analysis of Explainable Interfaces. In *Adjunct Proceedings of the 2024 Nordic Conference on Human-Computer Interaction*. 1–6.
- [21] Deepa Muralidhar, Rafik Belloum, and Ashwin Ashok. 2025. Operationalizing Selective Transparency Using Progressive Disclosure in Artificial Intelligence Clinical Diagnosis Systems. *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies* 204 (2025), 103591. doi:10.1016/j.ijhcs.2025.103591
- [22] Thu Nguyen, Alessandro Canossa, and Jichen Zhu. 2024. How human-centered explainable ai interface are designed and evaluated: A systematic survey. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2403.14496* (2024).
- [23] Ayano Okoso, Keisuke Otaki, Satoshi Koide, and Yukino Baba. 2025. Impact of Tone-Aware Explanations in Recommender Systems. *ACM Transactions on Recommender Systems* 3, 4, Article 55 (2025), 34 pages. doi:10.1145/3718101
- [24] Ayano Okoso, Mingzhe Yang, and Yukino Baba. 2025. Do Expressions Change Decisions? Exploring the Impact of AI's Explanation Tone on Decision-Making. In *Proceedings of the 2025 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. ACM, New York, NY, USA. doi:10.1145/3706598.3713744
- [25] Johannes Schneider. 2024. Explainable Generative AI (GenXAI): A Survey, Conceptualization, and Research Agenda. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2404.09554* (2024).
- [26] Mark Steyvers, Heliodoro Tejada, Aakriti Kumar, Catarina Belem, Sheer Karny, Xinyue Hu, Lukas Mayer, and Padhraic Smyth. 2025. What large language models know and what people think they know. *Nature Machine Intelligence* 7 (2025), 221–231. doi:10.1038/s42256-024-00976-7
- [27] Miles Turpin, Julian Michael, Ethan Perez, and Samuel R. Bowman. 2023. Language Models Don't Always Say What They Think: Unfaithful Explanations in Chain-of-Thought Prompting. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, Vol. 36.
- [28] Zhengtao Xu, Tianqi Song, and Yi-Chieh Lee. 2025. Confronting Verbalized Uncertainty: Understanding How LLM's Verbalized Uncertainty Influences Users in AI-Assisted Decision-Making. *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies* 197 (2025), 103455. doi:10.1016/j.ijhcs.2025.103455
- [29] Shunyu Yao, Dian Yu, Jeffrey Zhao, Izhak Shafran, Thomas L. Griffiths, Yuan Cao, and Karthik Narasimhan. 2023. Tree of Thoughts: Deliberate Problem Solving with Large Language Models. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems* 36.
- [30] Haiyan Zhao, Hanjie Chen, Fan Yang, Ninghao Liu, Huiqi Deng, Hengyi Cai, Shuaiqiang Wang, Dawei Yin, and Mengnan Du. 2024. Explainability for Large Language Models: A Survey. *ACM Transactions on Intelligent Systems and Technology* 15, 2 (2024), 1–38. doi:10.1145/3639372